

DETERMINING THE SPORTS PARTICIPATION MOTIVATIONS OF SKI ATHLETES

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Abstract:

The research was carried out to determine the motivation of sports participation for licensed skiers who have been actively working for at least 3 years within Bitlis, Erzurum, Hakkâri, Muş Youth and Sports Provincial Directorate. In the sample of this descriptive study, a total of 125 athletes between the ages of 11-19 were included. Frequency, percentage, and arithmetic average calculations were made statistically. Besides, according to normality test, since the data did not show normal distribution, the Mann Whitney U test was used for binary comparisons from nonparametric tests, and Kruskal Wallis H variance analysis was used to compare more than two groups. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The most important sub-dimensions of skating athletes' participation in sports are "Skill Development" ($1,17 \pm 0,327$), "Moving / Being Active" ($1,19 \pm 0,365$), "Physical Fitness" ($1,25 \pm 0,353$), "Competition" ($1,26 \pm 0,392$), "Entertainment" ($1,28 \pm 0,368$), "Success / Status" ($1,30 \pm 0,356$), "Team Membership / Spirit" ($1,32 \pm 0,430$) and "Friendship" ($1,38 \pm 0,458$) respectively. While there was no significant difference according to gender and age variables, "Team Membership / Spirit", "Friendship", "Physical Fitness" and "Entertainment" sub-dimensions were found to be significant differentiation. As a result, it can be said to have an important role for ski athletes to have a sense of togetherness, to evaluate their leisure time, to have a healthy and high moral strength through sport.

Keywords: skiing, sport, motivation

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1. Introduction

The concept of motivation is a concept that is based on self-determination (self-efficacy). In the theory of self-determination, the focus is on the reasons that speed up action in the individual (Terlemez, Şahin and Dilek, 2015). Motivation is an important factor that can determine participation in sports (Qurban et al., 2019), as well as the physical competence of the athlete, psychological competence also plays an important role in achieving success, and the most important of the psychological factors is the motivation of the individual (Yalçın, Turğut, Gacar and Çalık, 2017). The motivation to participate in sports is also one of the main factors that affect individuals' starting sports and sporting success in the process after they start (İlhan and Gencer, 2013). The word motivation is derived from the word "movere", which means "to act" in Latin. Motivation is defined as the process that initiates, directs and maintains targeted behavior. It includes biological, emotional, social and cognitive forces that activate behavior. Motivation is what causes us to act, such as drinking water to quench our thirst or reading books to gain knowledge (Goyal, 2015). In general, motivation is related to purposeful behavior. Because every individual has several requirements that he constantly tries to satisfy his needs. The motivation process begins with these needs in the individual. The individual will tend to certain behavior to meet these needs, and this behavior will be in the direction and purpose of fulfilling the needs of individuals (Şahin, 2004). Therefore, motivation positively affects emotional well-being as a result of the target behaviors that the individual wants to realize due to their wishes or needs (Demir and Cicioğlu, 2018).

Individuals can have many different sources of motivation to play sports. These sources of motivation are examined in three basic dimensions: internal, external and non-motivational. While individuals find peace and happiness in participation in sports constitute the source of intrinsic motivation, factors such as reward and punishment constitute external sources of motivation. The individual is affected by the source of lack of motivation when he/she cannot establish a cause and effect relation in participation in sports (Demir and İlhan, 2019). The motivated person turns thought into action, sets its goals and takes action to reach them (Soyer et al., 2010). The clearest examples of extrinsically motivated behaviors are those that are carried out to receive a concrete reward or to avoid a penalty (Deci and Ryan, 2008). Including the elements that make up the self-determination perspective in the hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, Vallerand (1997) proposes the new motivational series that is stated as "Social Factors → Psychological Mediators → Motivation Types Results". It can be seen that social factors (for example, success/failure, cooperation, coach feedback, etc.) affect athletes' perception of competence, autonomy, and relevance (i.e. psychological mediators) and this determines their motivation. Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation then lead to a series of consequences (excitement, athleticism, and persistence in sports). Researches reveal that athletes can be motivated both internally and externally (Vallerand and Losier, 1999).

Skiing is divided into alpine and northern discipline according to the areas in which it is performed and the types of deformation. These disciplines differ in their

physiological and physiological aspects, which should be made and possessed by athletes. The more endurance and aerobic power of the sportsmen dealing with skiing in the northern discipline come to the fore. Alpine discipline skiing, on the other hand, is more difficult than many sports in terms of the way it is made, although its anaerobic power is more prominent; Motoric features such as balance, coordination, strength, speed, endurance, and mobility must be performed very well (Kıyıcı, 2006, as cited in Alaeddinoğlu and Kaya, 2012). Therefore, it is clear that coaches will directly affect the technical, tactical, mental, spiritual and social aspects of athletes (Tatlıcı and Kırımoğlu, 2008). It is unpredictably difficult to motivate an athlete and at the same time keep the athlete motivated. Therefore, many factors directly affect the motivation level and success of the athlete. Factors that enable the athlete to succeed include social communication, (family and friends circle) income level, connection with his trainer and teammates (Özgün, Yaşartürk, Ayhan and Bozkuş, 2017). According to the literature review, the motives that determine individuals' tendency to sports as active or passive participants are positive stress, self-esteem, escape economy, entertainment, aesthetics, group environment, and family. Since there are different sources of motivation that affect individuals' orientation to sports, it is clear that different groups of individuals show different interactions and are influenced by different motives (İkizler and Tekin, 2008). However, as a result of the researches, it has been observed that the motivation of athletes who actively participate in physical education and sports programs is low. To encourage children to be more physically active and to adopt a healthy lifestyle, more research is needed to better understand the motivation processes and success behaviors of children. Therefore, more research on motivation in sports and physical activity is a requirement (Gao, Lee and Harrison, 2008). Societies aiming to increase the participation of individuals in sports have to deal with motivation to participate in sports (Tekkurşun, İlhan, Esentürk and Kan, 2018). Therefore, in this research, it was aimed to determine the motivation of sports participation motivations of athletes who are actively interested in ski sports for at least 3 years within Bitlis, Erzurum, Hakkâri and Muş provinces.

2. Method

2.1. Study Group

In this study, the data were obtained from 125 athletes between the ages of 11 and 19 who were actively interested in skiing for at least 3 years in the provinces of Bitlis, Erzurum, Hakkâri and Muş.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

As a data collection tool in the research; "Sports Participation Motivation Scale", which was developed by Gill et al. (1983) and whose validity and reliability study was performed by Oyar et al. (2001), was used. The "Personal Information Form" prepared by the researchers was used to collect information about the participants. The scale consists of 30 items and 8 sub-dimensions (Skill development, (3 items), Team Membership / Spirit (4 items), Entertainment (4 items), Friendship (3 items), Success / Status (5 items),

including the reasons for the individual's participation in sports. Physical Fitness / Energy Spending (5 items), Competition (3 items), Movement / Being Active (3 items).The reasons for the students' participation in sports were evaluated on the 3-point Likert type scale as "Unimportant (1), Less Important (2), Very Important (3)". The low scores obtained from the scale indicate that motivation to participate in sports is important, and high scores indicate that it is unimportant (Gill et al, 1983). The scale consists of 30 items and 8 sub-dimensions (Skill development (3 items), Team Membership / Spirit (4 items), Entertainment (4 items), Friendship (3 items), Success / Status (5 items), including the reasons for the individual's participation in sports. Physical Fitness / Energy Spending (5 items), Competition (3 items), Movement / Being Active (3 items).The reasons for the students' participation in sports were evaluated on the 3-point Likert type scale as "Unimportant (1), Less Important (2), Very Important (3)".The low scores obtained from the scale indicate that motivation to participate in sports is important, and high scores indicate that it is unimportant (Gill et al, 1983).

2.3. Data Analysis

The reliability analysis of the prepared scale was made. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was found at 0.778. Statistically, frequency, percentage, and arithmetic mean calculations were made. Also, according to the normality test, since the data did not show normal distribution, the Mann Whitney U test was used for binary comparisons from nonparametric tests, and Kruskal Wallis H variance analysis was used to compare more than two groups. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. Findings

Table 1: Distribution of ski athletes by gender and age

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	69	55,2
Female	56	44,8
Total	125	100,0

Gender	Frequency	Percent
11-13	18	14,4
14-16	63	50,4
17-19	44	35,2
Total	125	100,0

When Table 1 is examined, 69 (55.2%) of the 125 ski athletes participating in the study are men and 56 (44.89% are women). The age distribution of ski athletes varies between 11 and 19 years old. It is seen that the age group with the highest participation in the study was the 14-16 age group (50.4%), and the age group with the lowest participation was the 11-13 age group (14.4%).

Table 2: Average and Standard Deviation Values
 of Sports Participation Sub-Dimensions of Ski Athletes

Sub Dimensions	N	X̄	SS	Order of importance
Skill Development	125	1,17	0,327	1
Moving / Being Active	125	1,19	0,365	2
Physical Fitness	125	1,25	0,353	3
Competition	125	1,26	0,392	4
Entertainment	125	1,28	0,368	5
Success / Status	125	1,30	0,356	6
Team Membership Spirit	125	1,32	0,430	7
Friendship	125	1,38	0,458	8

When Table 2 is analyzed, the most important sub-dimensions of ski athletes' participation in sports are "Skill Development" ($1,17 \pm 0,327$), "Moving / Being Active" ($1,19 \pm 0,365$), "Physical Fitness" ($1,25 \pm 0,353$), "Competition" ($1,26 \pm 0,392$), "Entertainment" ($1,28 \pm 0,368$), "Success / Status" ($1,30 \pm 0,356$), "Team Membership / Spirit" ($1,32 \pm 0,430$) and "Friendship" ($1,38 \pm 0,458$) respectively.

Table 3: Statistical Analysis Results of the Difference between the Sports Participation Motive Scale Sub-Dimension Scores According to the Gender Status of Ski Athletes

Subdimensions	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	P
Skill Development	Male	69	61,27	4227,50	1812,500	-0,759	0,448
	Female	56	65,13	3647,50			
Team Membership Spirit	Male	69	59,32	4093,00	1678,000	-1,348	0,178
	Female	56	67,54	3782,00			
Entertainment	Male	69	66,78	4607,50	1671,500	-1,389	0,165
	Female	56	58,35	3267,50			
Friendship	Male	69	61,77	4262,00	1847,000	-0,449	0,653
	Female	56	64,52	3613,00			
Success / Status	Male	69	62,36	4303,00	1888,000	-0,229	0,819
	Female	56	63,79	3572,00			
Moving / Being Active	Male	69	67,21	4637,50	1641,500	-1,750	0,080
	Female	56	57,81	3237,50			
Physical Fitness	Male	69	59,78	4125,00	1710,000	-1,173	0,241
	Female	56	66,96	3750,00			
Competition	Male	69	63,35	4371,00	1908,000	-0,135	0,892
	Female	56	62,57	3504,00			

When Table 3 is examined, in order to determine whether ski athletes differ significantly between the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale for sports participation according to the gender variable, Mann Whitney U test was tested, and the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale of the sport were not statistically significant ($p > 0,05$).

Table 4: Statistical Analysis Results of the Difference Between the Sports Participation Motive Scale Sub-Dimension Scores according to the Age Variable of Ski Athletes

Subdimensions	Gender	N	Mean Rank	df	X ²	P
Skill Development	11-13	18	56,39	2	1,697	0,428
	14-16	63	62,41			
	17-19	44	66,55			
Team Membership Spirit	11-13	18	48,33	2	4,814	0,090
	14-16	63	62,90			
	17-19	44	69,14			
Entertainment	11-13	18	60,47	2	0,120	0,942
	14-16	63	63,56			
	17-19	44	63,24			
Friendship	11-13	18	61,53	2	1,526	0,466
	14-16	63	59,90			
	17-19	44	68,05			
Success / Status	11-13	18	60,58	2	0,268	0,875
	14-16	63	62,27			
	17-19	44	65,03			
Moving / Being Active	11-13	18	63,58	2	0,376	0,829
	14-16	63	64,37			
	17-19	44	60,81			
Physical Fitness	11-13	18	62,97	2	0,768	0,681
	14-16	63	60,60			
	17-19	44	66,45			
Competition	11-13	18	58,44	2	0,559	0,756
	14-16	63	62,83			
	17-19	44	65,10			

When Table 4 is examined, the Kruskal Wallis H test was performed to determine whether the ski athletes differed significantly between the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale of sports participation by age variable and there was no statistically significant difference between the groups in the sub-dimensions of motivation scale ($p>0,05$).

Table 5: Statistical Analysis Results of the Difference Between the Scale of Sports Participation Motivation Scale of Ski Athletes according to School Level Variable

Subdimensions	School Level	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	P
Skill Development	Secondary school	36	56,39	2030,00	1364,000	-1,660	0,097
	High school	89	65,67	5845,00			
Team Membership Spirit	Secondary school	36	50,76	1827,50	1161,500	-2,567	0,010*
	High school	89	67,95	6047,50			
Entertainment	Secondary school	36	59,56	2144,00	1478,000	-0,726	0,468
	High school	89	64,39	5731,00			
Friendship	Secondary school	36	53,75	1935,00	1269,000	-1,934	0,053
	High school	89	66,74	5940,00			
Success / Status	Secondary school	36	59,01	2124,50	1458,500	-0,819	0,413
	High school	89	64,61	5750,50			
Moving / Being Active	Secondary school	36	61,40	2210,50	1544,500	-0,380	0,704
	High school	89	63,65	5664,50			

Physical Fitness	Secondary school	36	62,49	2249,50	1583,500	-0,107	0,915
	High school	89	63,21	5625,50			
Competition	Secondary school	36	57,19	2059,00	1393,000	-1,293	0,196
	High school	89	65,35	5816,00			

When Table 5 is examined, the Mann Whitney U test tested whether ski athletes differ significantly between the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale according to the school level variable, and the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale for participation in sports; team membership/spirit (U= 1161,500; z=-2.567; p= 0,010<0.05) in favor of the sub-dimensions of the high school athletes were determined. As regards the other sub-dimensions of the motivation scale for participation in sport; there was no statistically significant difference between the groups (p>0,05).

Table 6: Statistical Analysis Results of the Difference Between Skiing Athletes' Scale of Sports Participation Motivation Scale According to the National Athlete Variable

Subdimensions	National athlete	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	P
Skill Development	Yes	11	69,82	768,00	552,000	-0,836	0,403
	No	114	62,34	7107,00			
Team Membership Spirit	Yes	11	77,09	848,00	472,000	-1,444	0,149
	No	114	61,64	7027,00			
Entertainment	Yes	11	80,77	888,50	431,500	-1,830	0,067
	No	114	61,29	6986,50			
Friendship	Yes	11	82,50	907,50	412,500	-1,991	0,046*
	No	114	61,12	6967,50			
Success / Status	Yes	11	57,00	627,00	561,000	-0,602	0,547
	No	114	63,58	7248,00			
Moving / Being Active	Yes	11	66,05	726,50	593,500	-0,354	0,723
	No	114	62,71	7148,50			
Physical Fitness	Yes	11	82,95	912,50	407,500	-2,036	0,042*
	No	114	61,07	6962,50			
Competition	Yes	11	62,36	686,00	620,000	-,069	0,945
	No	114	63,06	7189,00			

When Table 6 is examined, the Mann Whitney U test tested whether ski athletes differ significantly between the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale according to the national athlete variable and the sub-dimensions of the motivation scale; friendship (U= 412,500; z=-1.991; p= 0.046<0.05) and Physical Fitness (U=407,500;z=-2.036; p=0.042<0.05) in favor of the sub-dimensions of the national athletes were determined. In relation to the other sub-dimensions of the scale; there was no statistical meaning between the groups.

Table 7: Statistical Analysis Results of the Difference Between the Sports Participation Motivation Scale of Skiing Athletes according to Sports Branch Type Sub-Dimension Scores

Subdimensions	Sports Branch Type	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	P
Skill Development	Alp Discipline	64	63,80	4083,00	1901,000	-0,322	0,747
	Northern Discipline	61	62,16	3792,00			
Team Membership Spirit	Alp Discipline	64	65,46	4189,50	1794,500	-0,832	0,406

	Northern Discipline	61	60,42	3685,50			
Entertainment	Alp Discipline	64	54,18	3467,50	1387,500	-2,995	0,003*
	Northern Discipline	61	72,25	4407,50			
Friendship	Alp Discipline	64	61,34	3925,50	1845,500	-0,560	0,575
	Northern Discipline	61	64,75	3949,50			
Success / Status	Alp Discipline	64	62,47	3998,00	1918,000	-0,176	0,860
	Northern Discipline	61	63,56	3877,00			
Moving / Being Active	Alp Discipline	64	63,21	4045,50	1938,500	-0,081	0,936
	Northern Discipline	61	62,78	3829,50			
Physical Fitness	Alp Discipline	64	59,47	3806,00	1726,000	-1,188	0,235
	Northern Discipline	61	66,70	4069,00			
Competition	Alp Discipline	64	63,98	4094,50	1889,500	-0,350	0,726
	Northern Discipline	61	61,98	3780,50			

When Table 7 is analyzed, whether the ski athletes differed significantly between the sub-dimensions of the sport participation motivation scale according to the sports branch type variable was tested by using the Mann Whitney U test and among the sub dimensions of the sport participation motivation scale; significant differences were found in favor of the northern discipline sports type in the sub-dimension of entertainment ($U = 1387,500$; $z = -2,995$; $p = 0,003 < 0,05$). In relation to the other sub-dimensions of the scale; there was no statistical meaning between the groups.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The research was carried out to determine the motivation of licensed ski athletes who have been actively operating for at least 3 years within the body of Bitlis, Erzurum, Hakkâri, Muş Youth and Sports Provincial Directorate in terms of different variables. The most important sub-dimensions of ski athletes' participation in sports are "Skill Development" ($1,17 \pm 0,327$), "Moving / Being Active" ($1,19 \pm 0,365$), "Physical Fitness" ($1,25 \pm 0,353$), "Competition" ($1,26 \pm 0,392$), "Entertainment" ($1,28 \pm 0,368$), "Success / Status" ($1,30 \pm 0,356$), "Team Membership / Spirit" ($1,32 \pm 0,430$) respectively. At the end of the motivational factor of participation in sports, it was found that the sub-dimension of "Friendship" ($1,38 \pm 0,45$) was included. In this sense, it can be said that the research group's "skill development" and "acting / being active" sub-dimension of the sports they play in the most important order arises from the need of participants to act to discharge their energy and to improve their skills in their own sports branches. Thus, participants are often influenced by the drive to demonstrate physical skill, achieve the best individual result, or win an organized competition (Tekin et al., 2017). Our research result is similar to the findings of many studies in the literature. Şirin et al. (2008) tried to determine the factors affecting the motivation of sportsmen students attending the high school, as a result of the research, the most important factor in their motivation to participate in sports is "skill development" ($1,17 \pm 0,28$) and the least important factor is the average score is the "friendship" ($1,40 \pm 0,39$) subscale. According to the results of the study by Arslan and Altay (2009), in which the drive motives of male students in the primary schools in the central districts of Ankara were examined, the most important reasons for

participation in sports in all sports branches were identified as "Skill Development" and "Competition". In a study on tennis athletes, Kaman et al. (2017) found that the most important motivational factor in sports participation was "skill development". Altıntaş et al. (2010) investigated the motivation motives of young football players, and the participation motive sub-dimension they deemed the most important was determined as skill development.

When it was evaluated in terms of gender and age variable in the sports participation motivations of the research group, it was determined that there was no difference between the sports athletes' motivation in terms of all sub-dimensions. There are studies to support the results of our study in terms of gender and age variable. In the doctoral thesis of Karaç (2017), it was found that there was no significant difference between all sub-dimensions of the participation motivation scale of athletes according to the gender variable. As a result of a study in which Tekkurşun Demir, and İlhan (2019) examined the motivation of participation in sports for visually impaired athletes, no significant difference was found in the sub-dimensions of the motivation to participate in sports in terms of gender. As a result of a study conducted Polat, Hazar ve Eker (2018) on sports high school students and sports center members, it was determined that there was no significant difference in the motivation of participation in sports in terms of gender. Polat, Doğan and Mutlu (2018) showed that there was no significant difference between the motivation scale sub-dimensions of sports according to gender and age variable as a result of the study examining the motivation of participation of sports university students. As a result of the study in which Hazar et al. (2018) examined the motivation of high school students to participate in sports, there was no statistically significant difference in all sub-dimensions of the scale in terms of gender and age variable. Temel (2018) found that as a result of the research that examines the motivation of table tennis and wushu athletes in university teams, no significant difference was found between gender and age variables. This similarity can be said to be made by female and male ski athletes in the research group with close sources of motivation (İlhan and Gencer, 2013; Van Heerden, 2014; Polat, Hazar and Eker, 2018). However, some studies suggest findings opposite to these results. Afsanepurak et al. (2012) found that there was a significant difference between men and women as a result of a study in which they examined their motivation to participate in sports. Şirin et al. (2008) found a significant difference according to gender variable in their motivation to participate in sports as a result of their research on athletes who were trained in high school. Yıldırım (2017) found that there is a significant difference in terms of gender variable as a result of the study in which the athletes struggling in the university teams examined their motivation to participate in sports. Üstün and Kalkavan (2013) found that there was a significant difference in terms of gender variable as a result of the study in which the students of School of Physical Education and Sports examined the motivating factors of participating in recreational activities. As a result of the research examining the motivation of middle school students participating in support and training courses in Bingöl's (2017) master's thesis, it does not show parallelism with our study in terms of gender and age variable, but it is parallel with our study as it is determined that there are significant differences in

terms of sport type and branch variable. Holden et al. (2017) found that there was a significant difference in the sub-dimensions of motivation to participate in sports in the study in which male and female college athletes who played in baseball, basketball, cross country, football, golf, volleyball, tennis, athletics and volleyball teams examined their motivation to participate in sports.

Regular physical activities are important for child development. When studies in this field are examined, it is stated that there are differences between children who regularly participate in physical activities and children who do not. These regular physical activities contribute to the development of children in terms of physical, physiological, psychological, sociological and motoric features (Koç and Tekin, 2011). At the same time, long-term and regular movement training programs improve the physical fitness features of 10-12-year-old children positively (Saygın et al., 2005). It is a more positive use of the motivating factor in increasing the total physical activity time (Genç et al., 2011), which will directly affect the general physical, emotional and social development of the individual (Er et al., 2014). Gould (1982) stated that researches with motivation to participate in sports will be useful in preparing programs for coaches and managers, and in this way, coaches can meet the needs of individuals participating in the activities more easily and will have a positive effect on the psychological and motor development of individuals whose needs are determined and directed towards the activity in this direction (Yıldırım, 2017). As a result, a significant differentiation in the sub-dimensions of "Team Membership/Spirit", "Friendship", "Physical Fitness" and "Entertainment" can be said to have an important role for ski athletes to have a sense of togetherness, to evaluate their leisure time, to have a healthy and high moral strength through sport. In order to reduce physiological (obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, etc.) and psychological (stress, anxiety, depression, etc.), benefits can be developed by local governments to encourage individuals' participation in sports. As the data obtained as a limitation of this study was collected only from athletes actively interested in skiing in Eastern Anatolia (Bitlis, Erzurum, Hakkâri, and Muş) Region, it can be suggested that the study can expand the scope of the research with a larger sample group by conducting researches in groups similar to this group.

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